

DIALOGUE OF A RELATIVIST WITH A REALIST ABOUT THE RELATIVISTIC EFFECT OF “TIME DELAY”

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Annotation. The work presents a dialogue between a relativist and a realist about the relativistic effect of “time dilation”. This dialogue is based on fragments of a real discussion of the contradictions that the relativistic effect of “time dilation” leads to. During the dialogue, the relativist finds himself in a dead end, from which he is unable to get out. The essence of the contradiction that has arisen is that the same event occurs simultaneously at two completely different moments in time according to the same clock. This can't be true. The realist talks about the theory of aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally. It is this theory that should be used to solve practical problems associated with moving clocks, for example, problems in the field of satellite navigation systems.

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Introduction

The work presents a dialogue between a realist, representing the author, and a relativist, representing in the discussion a collective image of different people with whom it was necessary to discuss the issues of the relativistic effect of “time dilation” (in quotes, since the very fact of this effect, as it turns out during the discussion, is under great question).

During the discussion, the relativist comes to a dead end, from which he is unable to get out.

Relevance. Relativistic time dilation, if it exists, leads to a daily clock error of the GLONASS and GPS satellite navigation systems greater than 7000 ns (nanoseconds, 1 ns = 10⁻⁹ s). The value of relativistic time dilation for 86400 seconds, that is, per day, is calculated using the formula [1, p.19]

$$\text{Time dilation} = 86400 \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\text{Speed}}{\text{Speed of light}}\right)^2} \text{ seconds}$$

In this formula, «Speed» is the speed of movement of the navigation satellite. GLONASS and GPS satellites move at a speed of approximately 3.9 km/s. «Speed of light» is equal to approximately 299,792.5 km/s.

Moreover, in accordance with existing requirements, the limits of permissible shifts of the national time scale UTC(SU) relative to the UTC coordinated universal time scale are +/- 3.0 ns [2]. Thus, the accuracy of the modern state primary standard of units of time, frequency and

national time scale is more than *three orders of magnitude higher than* the value of the calculated daily “relativistic” clock drift of these satellite navigation systems. The contradictions that arise when calculating the relativistic effect of “time dilation” are an expression of a serious scientific problem, since the magnitude of the error that arises when calculating the deviation of satellite clocks due to this effect is so large that it cannot be neglected under any circumstances.

Dialogue between a relativist and a realist about relativistic “time dilation”

R e l i t i v i s t. I became superficially acquainted with the theory of aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, which was confirmed experimentally [3-7]. Nevertheless, there is no reason to doubt the truth of SRT in general, and the reliability of the effect of relativistic time dilation, in particular.

R e a l i s t. Well, let's do a thought experiment with clocks moving relative to each other in order to understand the relativistic “time dilation”.

R e l i t i v i s t. Agree.

R e a l i s t. Let relative to each other with speed v two rows of clocks move (Fig. 1). The clocks in each row are synchronized with each other. At the moment of time “00:00:00” (the beginning of the next day), according to the clocks of one row of synchronized clocks, the clocks of the other row are also set to “00:00:00” according to the readings of the clocks of the opposite row closest to them.

Fig. 1. Clock problem

Speed v relative motion of the rows is equal to 0.99 speed of light.

Clock A in the front row and clock B in the second row they are equipped with a (hypothetical) limit switch that is activated when these clocks approach (pass each other). When the limit switch is triggered, clock A and B are stopped (as a stopwatch is stopped), after which these watches can be moved so that their readings can be compared by some researcher.

From the point of view of clock A , clock B moving towards them at speed v (Fig. 2) .

Fig. 2.

Question 1 . Calculate what time clock *B* will show at the moment of stopping when meeting with clock *A* , if at the meeting clock *A* will show 100 seconds (“00:01:40,000”)? The answer to this question must be found using SRT formulas indicating the source (preferably the works of Einstein).

R e l i t i v i s t. This is an elementary, simplest task for a service station.

According to SRT [1, p.19], the answer can be found using the formula

$$\text{Время}_B = \text{Время}_A \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\text{Скорость}}{\text{Скорость света}}\right)^2} = 100 \times \sqrt{1 - 0,99^2} = 14,1 \text{ seconds}$$

In this formula, “*Время_A*” and “*Время_B*” are the time of clocks *A* and *B* , respectively, at the meeting; “*Скорость*” – speed of movement of the clock.

The answer you are looking for is: Clock *B*, when meeting with Clock *A*, will show 14.1 seconds.

R e a l i s t. Let's write down your answer, highlighting it in a frame:

B reading at meeting 14.1 seconds

Let us now consider this same situation from the other side. From the point of view of clock *B* watch *A* moving towards them at speed *v*(Fig. 3) .

Fig. 3.

Question 2 . How much time will watch *A* show at the moment of stopping when meeting with watch *B* , if when meeting, watch *B* shows 14.1 seconds (the number of seconds of watch *B* when stopping)? The answer to this question must be found using SRT formulas indicating the source (preferably the works of Einstein).

R e l i t i v i s t. In this case, you need to use a similar formula

$$\text{Time}_A = \text{Time}_B \times \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\text{Speed}}{\text{Speed of light}}\right)^2} = 14,1 \times \sqrt{1 - 0,99^2} = 1,99 \text{ seconds}$$

The answer is: Clock *A*, when meeting Clock *B*, will show 1.99 seconds.

R e a l i s t. Let's write down your answer, highlighting it in a frame:

clock reading *A* at meeting 1.99 seconds

After stopping clocks *A* and *B* at the moment of their meeting (Fig. 1), these watches were transferred to some researcher to compare their readings.

Question 3.

What readings from this watch will the researcher record?

R e l i t i v i s t. According to the calculations made, the readings of the watch after it stops during the meeting will be as follows (question 1)

clock reading A :	100 seconds
clock B :	14.1 seconds

Thus, due to motion, clock B *will* lag behind clock A . This is the essence of relativistic time dilation: moving clocks go slower than stationary ones.

R e a l i s t. Now pay attention to the following. According to your calculations using SRT, if the clock stops at the moment of the meeting, clock A will show 100 seconds, and clock B will show 14.1 seconds. But all movement is relative. Clock B moves relative to clock A , but at the same time (that is, simultaneously) clock A *moves* relative to clock B . From the point of view of an observer moving with clock A , this clock is stationary, and clock B is moving. But from the point of view of an observer moving with clock B , this clock is motionless, and clock A is moving.

Solving the problem from the point of view of clock B (question 2), you came to the conclusion that when the clocks meet, clock B will read 14.1 seconds, and clock A – 1.99 seconds.

In other words, stopped clock B will show 14.1 seconds, and stopped clock A will show 100 seconds (your answer to question 1), and at the same time (at the same time) 1.99 seconds (your answer to question 2).

This results in *a contradiction*: clock A stopped upon meeting will show 100 seconds and 1.99 seconds at the same time.

Obviously, this cannot be.

R e l i t i v i s t. I admit, you “pushed me to the wall,” I don’t know how to explain it. But I think, nevertheless, that this is another paradox of the theory of relativity, which can be explained. Apparently, it’s all about the relativity of simultaneity. According to the principle of “relativity of simultaneity”, if two events separated in space are observed simultaneously in a reference frame “moving” with speed, then they will be observed non-simultaneous relative to the “stationary” frame.

R e a l i s t. Indeed, in SRT there is the concept of “relativity of simultaneity”. But even in SRT this concept is applicable only if there are two events separated in space. In our case, there is only one event: two clocks A and B meet nearby when moving relative to each other, and at the moment of approaching they stop. The clock stops only once. Therefore, the same stopped clock cannot have two readings at the same time.

That is why the relativity of simultaneity in this case does not help explain the contradiction that has arisen.

R e l i t i v i s t. I have to agree with you.

R e a l i s t. The contradictions that relativistic “time dilation” leads to are that

1. One event occurs simultaneously at two completely different points in time on the same clock;

2. The same clock at the same point in time (the moment the event occurs) shows two completely different times.

In accordance with the law of non-contradiction of formal logic, both the first and the second are impossible. In a more general sense, the contradiction that has arisen is that

3. Calculation of the same physical quantity (the time of occurrence of one event using the same clock) in different ways with the same initial data leads to completely different values that are completely incompatible with each other.

It inevitably follows from this that SRT, when calculating relativistic “time dilation”, gives erroneous and unreliable results.

R e l i t i v i s t. What to do then? How then to solve problems when calculating the readings of a moving clock?

R e a l i s t. Fortunately, for these purposes, the theory of aberration has been developed - the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally. I recommend that you get to know it better and, to solve practical problems, use not the SRT, which gives errors, but the theory of aberration.

Conclusion

The dialogue between the realist (the author) and the relativist showed the following. Relativistic “time dilation”, the essence of which is that moving clocks go slower than stationary ones, leads to the following contradictions:

1. One event occurs simultaneously at two completely different points in time on the same clock;
2. The same clock at the same moment in time (the moment of occurrence of one event) shows two completely different times.
3. Calculation of the same physical quantity in different ways with the same initial data leads to completely different values that are completely incompatible with each other.

This is impossible. This is why STR inevitably gives erroneous results when calculating the relativistic clock correction caused by the effect of relativistic “time dilation”.

Instead of SRT, when calculating the progress of moving clocks, to eliminate errors, one should use the theory of aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally [3-7].

Please send your comments and suggestions regarding this work by email. mail: al.plyasovskih@yandex.ru

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